

The mutillid wasp collection of the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia (Hymenoptera: Mutillidae)

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Abstract. The family Mutillidae from the collection of the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia has been found to comprise 42 species from 18 genera. The fore wing venation is re-evaluated as having no taxonomical value to distinguish *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier), *K. thracia* (Suárez), and *K. beaumonti* (Invrea). *Skorikovia radoszkovskii* (Skorikov) is reported for the first time for Turkey. *Krombeinella nigriceps nigriceps* (S. Saunders), *Dentilla curtiventris* (Er. André), *Physetopoda dagbestanica* (Radoszkowski), *Ph. lucasii lucasii* (F. Smith), *Ph. pusilla* (Klug), *Skorikovia pliginskiji* (Skorikov), *Smicromyrme ausonia ausonia* Invrea, *Trogaspidia catanensis* (Rossi), *Cystomutilla ruficeps* (F. Smith) and *Stenomutilla bizonata* (F. Smith) are reported for the first time for Bulgaria.

Key words: Museum collections, Hymenoptera, Mutillidae, Bulgaria

Introduction

Mutillidae, a peculiar family of Aculeate Hymenoptera with representatives found all over the continents, has got little attention from the Bulgarian zoologists. This is the main reason why the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia houses a rather small collection of mutillids which contains 190 specimens belonging to 42 species from 18 genera. Two authors especially, Alexander Skorikov and Neno Atanassov have greatly contributed to the gathering of the present Mutillidae collection. Somewhere between 1925 and 1935 the Ukrainian hydrobiologist and entomologist Skorikov donated to the Museum eleven specimens originating mainly from Transcaucasia and Middle Asia. He also determined a lot of the Bulgarian mutillid material. His material from Transcaucasia and Middle Asia comprises individuals in some cases from the type localities of taxa, which at present are either considered synonyms or of changed taxonomic rank (*Myrmilla sarmatica* Skorikov, *Craspedopyga sarafschani* Radoszkowski var. *bucharensis* Skorikov, *Dasylabris duplicolor* Skorikov, *Craspedopyga mauropsis* Skorikov). It is rather certain that these specimens are part of the syntype series, even though they have not been designated lately (LELEJ, 1985: 106, 126, 127, 132). The Bulgarian entomologist and theriologist Atanassov contributed 32 mutillid specimens to the museum collection from almost all over the Bulgarian territory. His material served as a basis for his own research on Bulgarian mutillids, the results of which appeared in several publications between 1951 and 1972, the most important of which is the one from 1951 (ATANASSOV, 1951). Iwan Buresch and Pencho Drensky collected a relatively big amount of homogenous material mainly from the

genera *Myrmilla* Wesmæl, *Mutilla* Linnaeus, *Nemka* Lelej, and *Physetopoda* Schuster, each one of them enriching the collection with 14 and 23 specimens respectively.

Chronologically the first mutillid material for the museum collection (four specimens) came from France as a part of a collection bought from the trade firm Deyrolle somewhere at the end of the 19th century. The enrichment of the collection was further conducted as a part of arranging the insect collection of the Entomological Station at the Royal Natural History Museum. The Station was founded in 1905 and in fact ceased to exist independently in 1938 (POPOV, 1991). Mutillid material from different regions in Bulgaria or neighboring countries was collected at that time by curators and/or members of the Entomological Station - Buresch, Deltcho Iltchev, Drensky, Krustyo Touleshkov, and Atanassov. A lot of material was contributed after buying the collections of the forest-guard Julius Milde (in 1918), the schoolteachers Peter Tchorbadzhieff (in 1919) and Nikola Nedjalkov (in 1920), as well as that of one of the founders of the Bulgarian Entomological Society Dimitur Yoakimov (in 1922). This material was determined in the early years of the 20th century by Hans Bischoff and was reported in the first faunistical work dedicated to the family Mutillidae from Bulgaria and some neighboring countries (BURESCH, 1924). In the period from 1938 up to the middle of the 60ies, Drensky, Touleschkov, Alexander Drenowski, Hristo Lukov, and Atanassov donated still more material from Bulgaria and few specimens came from the collections of Nikolay Karnozhitski, Nikolay Vihodcevsky, and Nenko Radeff. Up to the middle of the 70ies, only two specimens were donated by Atanassov and Georgi Peshev. Since then the collection has been filled with several specimens from the collection of Alexi Popov as well as from the collections of Michail Josifov and Toshko Ljubomirov.

At present the collection is arranged in three boxes and contains almost all the material on which the faunistical reports on Mutillidae from Bulgaria until now are based.

Material and methods

The present study is based on the examination of 190 adult specimens of Mutillidae, borrowed from the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia. Specimens were relaxed in humidifier, removed from the pin, and dewaxed by soaking them in isopropanole. The specimens were further pinned up using new insect pins. The new preparation aimed to ensure that the important taxonomic characters were visible viz., free clypeal margin, inner mandibular edge, pygidial field etc. In some cases the genital preparations were made (e.g. in males of *Physetopoda*, *Skorikovia*, *Smicromyrme*, *Dasylabris*, *Stenomutilla* among others). Dried adult specimens were examined with a Technival and Leica stereoscopic microscopes under magnification 10-50x. The terms used to describe the thoracic parts in *Stenomutilla bizonata* (F. Smith), primarily follow those in LELEJ (1985). The wing venation terminology adopted for *Krombeinella longicollis* follows the one on the generalized Ampulicidae member *Aphelotoma rufiventris* R. Turner and was taken from MELO (1999: 46, fig. 19).

The present list of the mutillid collection provides information only about localities, sex and number of the specimens for each species, as well as the name of the collector. Information about previous determinations on the collection material is omitted. Even though almost 80 percent of the material was determined beforehand, the aim of the present work is not to make a revision of the group on an indigenous level but to prepare an inventory list of the available material. Mutillids, which originate from the collection of Nikola Nedjalkov, have no collector name on the labels. Mentioning the names of the collectors in Nedjalkov's mutillid material, I rely completely on the

Table 1
List of some old localities written on the labels in the collection and their recent equivalents

Old locality on original label	Actualized locality	Geographic Coordinates	Country
Ali-Botoush-Macedonia	Slavyanka Mountain(northern slopes)	41° 23'N; 25° 44'E	Bulgaria
Balkan-Yumruk Tchal	Kaloferska Planina Mountain: Botev Vruh peak	42° 42'N; 24° 55'E	Bulgaria
Burgas-Poda	Black Sea coast: NE Mandra reservoir	42° 27'N; 27° 27'E	Bulgaria
Centralni Rodopi-Ladjani	Velingrad town: Ludzhene suburb	42° 01'N; 24° 00'E	Bulgaria
Corfu	Kerkira Island: Kerkira	39° 37'N; 19° 55'E	Greece
Kourillo	Iskar valley: Novi Iskar town	42° 47'N; 23° 21'E	Bulgaria
Kressna Deffile-Sali Aga	Strouma valley: Kressna town	41° 43'N; 23° 08'E	Bulgaria
Kyupriya	Black Sea coast: Primorsko	42° 16'N; 27° 46'E	Bulgaria
Makri bai Dede Agatsch	Évros province: Makri village	40° 51'N; 25° 44'E	Greece
Marmo Pole	Strouma valley: Marino Pole village	41° 25'N; 23° 21'E	Bulgaria
Mitchourin	Black Sea coast: Tzarevo town	42° 10'N; 27° 51'E	Bulgaria
Newrokop	Messta valley: Gotse Delchev town	41° 34'N; 23° 43'E	Bulgaria
Otmanlij, Burgassko	Black Sea coast: S Bourgass	42° 27'N; 27° 33'E	Bulgaria
Rhodopi-Banya-Kosstenets	Rila Mountain: NE Kosstenets town	42° 17'N; 23° 52'E	Bulgaria
Sarepta	Volga valley: SW Volgograd	48° 31'N; 44° 29'E	Russia
Soleno Dere	Rila Mountain: S Borovets-1600m	42° 13'N; 23° 35'E	Bulgaria
Tcham Kouriya	Rila Mountain: Borovets	42° 16'N; 23° 34'E	Bulgaria
Thracien, Badoma	Évros province: N Alexandroupolis	40° 54'N; 25° 53'E	Greece
Tsentralni Rhodopi, Foten	Rhodopi Mountains: Fotinovo village	41° 52'N; 24° 21'E	Bulgaria
Varna-Makssouda	Black Sea coast: S Varnensko Ezero lake	43° 11'N; 27° 51'E	Bulgaria
Vitoscha - H. Fonfon	Vitosha Mountain: SW Zlatni Mostove-1510m	42° 36'N; 23° 14'E	Bulgaria
Zehtin Borun	Black Sea coast: Maslen Nos cape	42° 18'N; 27° 47'E	Bulgaria

explanations given by Nedjalkov himself (NEDJALKOV, 1914: 181-182). Some localities written on the labels are too old, incorrect and are not used today in geographical maps and indices. Aiming to facilitate the reader when using the data on these localities, they are presented by their present names in the list. These localities are enumerated in Table 1 both with their original names (written on the labels) and their recent equivalent names. New mutillid species for the corresponding country (Bulgaria or Turkey) are marked with an asterisk.

The Mutillid Collection

1. *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier, 1889)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Razgradski Visotchini Heights: Trubatch Village, 3.-18. VII. 1999, leg. K. Ivanov; 2♂♂: Maritsa Valley: Plovdiv-160m, 17.-25. VIII. 1999, leg. S. Petrov.

The three males of *K. longicollis* show considerable intraspecific variation in fore wing venation, especially in the shape of the second submarginal cell. One specimen from Plovdiv has a second submarginal cell subtrapezoidal caused by the connection of 2r-rs with Rs before 2rs-m (Fig. 1). The specimen from Trubatch Village has a second submarginal cell subtriangular caused by the interstitial position of 2r-rs to 2rs-m (Fig. 2). Finally, another specimen from Plovdiv has a second submarginal cell petiolate caused by the connection of 2r-rs with Rs after 2rs-m (Fig. 3).

The shape of the second submarginal cell was applied by LELEJ (1985: 58) to distinguish than the males of the closely relatives *K. thracia* (Suárez), *K. longicollis* (Tournier), and *K. beaumonti* (Invrea). The presence of the above mentioned degree of variation in the shape of this cell only within *K. longicollis* indicates that this character can by no means be of use to distinguish the former three species. The most significant criterion to distinguish *K. longicollis* from its close relatives, bearing distinct forecoxal spur, seems to be the shape of the hypopygium. Furthermore, the three examined specimens of *K. longicollis* have a hypopygium, which corresponds quite well to the Lelej's drawing (LELEJ, 1985: 59, figure 5).

*2. *Krombeinella nigriceps nigriceps* (S. Saunders, 1850)

Material: 1♀: BULGARIA, Zemenski Prolom Gorge: Ruzhdavitsa Village, 15. VIII.-15. IX. 1997, leg. T. Minkova.

3. *Myrmosa atra atra* Panzer, 1801

Material: 1♀: BULGARIA, Rila Mountain: N of Parangalitsa reserve-1420m, 20. VIII. 1997, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

4. *Paramyrmosa brunnipes* (Lepelletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1845)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Sofia: Dragalevtzi suburb, leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1♂: Black Sea coast: Masslen Nos cape, 16. VI. 1933, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1♂: Nishava Valley: Godetch, 29. VI. 1965, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♀: Vitosha Mountain: SW of Metcha Doupka Peak-1490m, 29. VII. 1999, leg. T. Ljubomirov; 1♀: Vitosha Mountain: N Petrouss Peak-1300m, 29. VII. 1999, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

5. *Myrmilla (Myrmilla) calva* (Villers, 1789)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Vitosha Mountain: Vladaya Village, leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1♀: Sofia, VII. 1904, leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, VII. 1906, leg. K. Seizov; 1♀: Black Sea coast:

Fig. 1. *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier) - fore wing venation in a specimen from Plovdiv.

Fig. 2. *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier) - fore wing venation in a specimen from Razgradski Visotchini Heights.

Fig. 3. *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier) - fore wing venation in a specimen from Plovdiv.

Varna, 7. VII. 1937, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, 23. IX. 1949; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: Shevovitsa-1250m, 9. X. 1999, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

6. *Myrmilla* (*Myrmilla*) *caucasica* (Kolenati, 1846)

Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Razgradski Visotchini Heights: Trubatch Village, 8.-22. VIII. 1999, leg. K. Ivanov; 1 ♀: Stara Zagora, VII. 1905, leg. F. Broumev; 1 ♀: Ihtiman, VI. 1907, leg. St. Kozarov; 1 ♀: Troyan-1000m, VII. 1908; 1 ♀: TURKEY, Tekirdagh province: Ganos Peak-800m, 6. V. 1913, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: GREECE, Évros province: N Alexandroupolis, 1. VII. 1919, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Kaloferska Planina Mountain: Botev Vruh Peak, 26. V. 1924; 2 ♀♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, 7. VII. 1937, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Isskar Valley: Lakatnik railway station, 11. V. 1952; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: S Bourgas, 8. VI. 1954, leg.: N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Stara Zagora, 4. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Maluk Kozhuh hills, 30. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: W Stara Planina Mountains: Rakovishki Manastir, 5. V. 1965, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Lozenska Planina Mountain: NW Pasarel Village-820m, 21. VI. 1997, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

7. *Myrmilla (Myrmilla) lezginica* (Radoszkowski, 1885)

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Stara Zagora, VII. 1905, leg. F. Broumev; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Masslen Nos cape, 17. VI. 1933, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: NE of Mandra reservoir, 9. VI. 1954, leg. N. Atanassov.

8. *Myrmilla (Pseudomutilla) capitata* (Lucas, 1846)

Material: 2 ♀ ♀: locality not indicated.

9. *Myrmilla (Pseudomutilla) glabrata* (Fabricius, 1775)

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Sofia, 16. VI. 1906, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: Iskar Valley: Pantcharevo Village, VII. 1906, leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀: UKRAINE, Poltavskaya Oblast district: Brussnya, 25. VIII. 1923, leg. Belgovskij; 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Velingrad: Ludzhene suburb, 2. VIII. 1925, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, 7. VII. 1937, leg. P. Drensky.

10. *Myrmilla (Pseudomutilla) vutshetitshi* Skorikov, 1927

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Stara Zagora, VII. 1906, leg. F. Broumev; 1 ♀: Kaloferska Planina Mountain: Botev Vruh Peak-1600m, 26. V. 1924; 1 ♀: Velingrad: Ludzhene suburb, 2. VIII. 1925, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♂: Zlatisko-Tetevenska Planina Mountain: S Broussen Village-750m, 17. X. 1995, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

11. *Platymyrmilla quinquefasciata* (Olivier, 1811)

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: Primorsko, 16. V. 1930, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Dobroudzha: Vidno Village, 3. VII. 1952, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: NE Mandra reservoir, 9. VI. 1954, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Thracian lowland: nearby Harmanli, 18. VII. 1962, leg. N. Atanassov.

12. *Ctenotilla caeca* (Radoszkovsky, 1879)

Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Maleshevska Planina Mountain: SW of Gorna Breznitsa Village-830m, 9. VII. 2002, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

13. *Mutilla europaea* Linnaeus, 1758

Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Rhodopes: VII. 1906, leg. St. Kozarov; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: Kostenets-1000m, 1. VII. 1912, leg. A. Urumova; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: Belmeken-1200m, 1. VII. 1912, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: S Borovets-1600m, 15. VIII. 1932, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: Kostenets-1500m, 8.-14. VII. 1935, leg. Kr. Touleschkov; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: Borovets-1400m, 1. VII. 1955, leg. Iw. Buresch & A. Popov; 1 ♂: Rila Mountain: Borovets-1400m, 5. VIII. 1959, leg. A. Popov; 1 ♂: Vitosha Mountain: Koupenska Reka riverside-1800m, 29. VII. 1999, leg. T. Ljubomirov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets, VIII. 1905, leg. St. Kozarov; 2 ♀ ♀: Rila Mountain: Kostenets, 15. V. 1909, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: NE of Kostenets, 30. V. 1909, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Kosstenets, 14. V. 1912, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: Kaloferska Planina Mountain: Botev Vruh Peak-1600m, 26. V. 1924; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets, 27. VII. 1924; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: NE of Kostenets town, 5. VII. 1928, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Central Balkan Mountains, 13. VII. 1928, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Belasitsa Mountain: 6. VI. 1929, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Kostenets, 20. VII. 1933, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 2 ♀ ♀: Rila Mountain: Kostenets-1500m, 8.-14. VII. 1935, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets-2000m, 20. VIII. 1935, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets-2000m, 20. VII. 1938, leg. Iw. Buresch; 2 ♀ ♀:

Vitosha Mountain-1300m, 11. VI. 1939, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain, 1300-1400m, 12. VIII. 1948, leg. Al. Drenowski; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: Aleko hut-1800m, 13. VIII. 1948, leg. Al. Drenowski; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain, 1400-1600m, 9. VII. 1950, leg. Al. Drenowski; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets-1400m, 15. VII. 1952, leg. Iw. Buresch & A. Popov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets-1400m, 1. VIII. 1954, leg. Iw. Buresch & A. Popov; 3 ♀ ♀: Vitosha Mountain-1450m, 12. VII. 1955, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Rila Mountain: Borovets-1400m, 25. VII. 1958, leg. A. Popov; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: SW of Zlatni Mostove-1510m, 29. V. 1959, leg. N. Vihodcevsky; 1 ♀: Thracian lowland: Tchirpan, 3. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Maluk Kozhuh hills, 30. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Assenovgrad, 1. VI. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Rhodopes: Perelik Peak, 7. VII. 1962, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Rhodopes: Preslapa Peak-1780m, 27. VII. 1969, leg. G. Peshev; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: Tcherni Vruh Peak-2200m, 5. VII-6. VIII. 1999, leg. O. Mikov; 1 ♀: Rhodopes: Belovo, leg. J. Milde; 1 ♀: no locality data.

14. *Mutilla marginata* Baer, 1848

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Sofia, 1902, leg. Iw. Buresch.

15. *Mutilla quinque maculata* Cyrillo, 1787

Material: 1 ♀: GREECE: Évros province: N Alexandroúpolis, 1. VII. 1919, leg. D. Joakimov.

16. *Ronisia barbara* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material: 1 ♀: locality not indicated.

17. *Ronisia brutia brutia* (Petagna, 1787)

Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Rhodopes: Batchkovo Village, VII. 1906, leg. St. Kozarov; 1 ♀: MACEDONIA, Doyran, VII. 1917, leg. Taraktchiev; 1 ♀: GREECE, Olympus Mountain-800m, 20. VII. 1937, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Ivaylovgrad: Ludzha sub., 26. IX. 1997, leg. E. Manassieva.

18. *Tropidotilla litoralis* (Petagna, 1787)

Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Rhodopes: Batchkovo Village, VIII. 1906, leg. St. Kozarov; 1 ♂: Sakar Mountain: Ravna Gora Village, 28. V-17. VI; 1 ♀: Stara Zagora, VII. 1905, leg. St. Kozarov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Burgas, VII. 1905, leg. D. Vezhev; 1 ♀: Slavyanka Mountain: 1. VIII. 1920; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Primorsko, 18. V. 1931, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Rezovo Village, 11. VI. 1933, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Masslen Nos cape, 17. VI. 1933, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: GREECE, Olympus Mountain-800m, 20. VIII. 1937, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 2 ♀ ♀: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: St. Konstantin & Helena, 15. VII. 1939, leg. P. Drensky; 2 ♀ ♀: Black Sea coast: Tzarevo, 4. VI. 1954, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Tzarevo, 4. VI. 1954, leg. G. Peshev; 1 ♀: Strouma Valley: Kresnensko Defile Gorge, 27. VI. 1958, leg. Hr. Loukov; 1 ♀: Strouma Valley: Marino Pole Village, 29. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Russe, 26. VI. 1963, leg. A. Popov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: St. Konstantin & Helena, 15. VII. 1993, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

*19. *Dentilla curtiventris* (Er. André, 1901)

Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Strouma Valley: Sheytan Dere Gorge, 1. VIII. 2002, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

20. *Nemka viduata bartholomaei* (Radoszkovsky, 1865)

Material: 1 ♂: AZERBAIJAN: Mouganskaya Step steppe: Alpaout, 14. VII. 1910, leg. K. Satounin.

21. *Nemka viduata viduata* (Pallas, 1773)

Material: 1♂: RUSSIA, Volga Valley: SW of Volgograd, 1865, leg. Th. Becker; 1♂: GREECE, Kerkira Island: Kerkira, 25. VI. 1909; 1♂: BULGARIA, Strouma Valley: Kresna town, 4. VII. 1932. leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1♂: Black Sea coast: St. Konstantin & Helena, 15. VII. 1939, leg. P. Drensky; 1♂: Black Sea coast: Rhopotamo riverside, 7. VII. 1964, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♀: Iskar Valley: Pantcharevo Village, VII. 1906. leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, 7. VII. 1937. leg. P. Drensky; 1♀: Black Sea coast: Varna, 6. VIII. 1938. leg. N. Atanassov; 1♀: Black Sea coast: Varna: S Varnensko Ezero lake, 20. VIII. 1954, leg. Iw. Buresch & A. Popov; 1♀: Harmanli, leg. Iw. Buresch & A. Popov.

*22. *Physetopoda daghestanica* (Radoszkowski, 1885)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Pirin Mountain: Bayovi Douпки, VIII. 1932, leg. P. Drensky; 1♂: Vitosha Mountain: Bosnek Village-940m, 22.-29. VII. 1999, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

23. *Physetopoda balensis* (Fabricius, 1787)

Material: 2♂♂: BULGARIA, Iskar Valley: Pantcharevo Village, VII. 1905. leg. N. Nedjalkov; 1♂: Stara Zagora, VII. 1906. leg. St. Kozarov; 1♂: GREECE, Souflion, 12. VII. 1914, D. Iltchev; 1♂: BULGARIA, Stara Planina Mountains: Berkovitsa, 1. VIII. 1935, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♂: Iskar Valley: Novi Iskar, 10. VIII. 1944, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♀: Sofia: Vrazhdebna sub. 30. IV.-15. V, 2002, leg. R. Kostova & R. Bektchiev.

*24. *Physetopoda lucasii lucasii* (F. Smith, 1855)

Material: 1♀: BULGARIA, Pirin Mountain: Okaden Peak-2472m, VIII, 1932, leg. P. Drensky.

*25. *Physetopoda pusilla* (Klug, 1835)

Material: 1♀: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: Varna, 7. VII. 1937, leg. P. Drensky; 1♀: Sofia, 3.-17. IV. 2002, leg. R. Kostova & R. Bektchiev.

26. *Physetopoda scutellaris* (Latreille, 1792)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Iskar Valley: Pantcharevo Village, VII. 1906. leg. N. Nedjalkov.

*27. *Skorikovia pliginskiji* (Lelej, 1984)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: Obzor, 7. VII. 1951, leg. N. Atanassov.

*28. *Skorikovia radoszkovskii* (Skorikov, 1935)

Material: 1♂: TURKEY, Nevcehir province: Görehme-1100-1300m, 16. VII. 1991, leg. S. Beshkov. *S. radoszkovskii* was known until now to inhabit the area between the Black and the Caspian seas (LELEJ, 2002). The locality cited here enlarges at least twice the range of this newly reported for Turkey species.

*29. *Smicromyrme (Astomyrme) ausonia ausonia* Invrea, 1950

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Stara Zagora, VII. 1907, leg. F. Broumev; 1♂: Assenovgrad. 19. VII. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♂: Zemenski Prolom Gorge: E Polska Skakavitsa Village, 21. VIII. 1999, leg. I. Gionov.

30. *Smicromyrme (Smicromyrme) ruficollis ruficollis* (Fabricius, 1793)
Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Belassitsa Mountain: Kolarovo Village, 21. VII. 1930, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Assenovgrad. 19. VII. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov.
31. *Smicromyrme (Smicromyrme) rufipes* (Fabricius, 1787)
Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: Varna, 7. VII. 1937, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: locality not indicated.
- *32. *Trogaspidia catanensis* (Rossi, 1794)
Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Hasskovo, VII. 1896, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: Harmanli, 28. V. 1930, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: Black Sea coast: Maslen Nos cape, 17. VI. 1933, leg. Kr. Touleshkov.
33. *Trogaspidia fedtschenkoi* (Radoszkowsky, 1877)
Material: 1 ♂: TURKMENISTAN, Farab, 20. VI. 1912, leg. A. Hohlbeke; 1 ♀: Kara Sengir, 19. VI. 1911, leg. N. Zarudnij.
- *34. *Cystomutilla ruficeps* (F. Smith, 1855)
Material: 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Maleshevska Planina Mountain: E Gorna Breznitsa Village-410m, 16. VI. 2002, leg. T. Ljubomirov.
35. *Dasylabris (Craspedopyga) manderstiernii manderstiernii* (Radoszkowsky, 1865)
Material: 1 ♀: Transcaucasia¹.
36. *Dasylabris (Dasylabris) bucharensis* (Skorikov, 1935)
Material: 1 ♀: UZBEKISTAN, SW Bukhara: Kara-Kul, 11. VII. 1928, A. Gerasimov (Fig. 4).
37. *Dasylabris (Dasylabris) maura armeniaca* (Kolenati, 1846)
Material: 1 ♀: Caucasus Mountain.
38. *Dasylabris (Dasylabris) maura maura* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Material: 1 ♂: BULGARIA, Black Sea coast: Varna, 14. VII. 1943, leg. N. Karnozhitski; 1 ♂: Maritsa Valley: Dossitevo Village, 30. VI. 1955, leg. M. Josifov; 1 ♂: Petritch, 22. VI. 1957, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: 17. VIII. 1904, leg. D. Joakimov; 1 ♀: TURKEY, Tekirdagh province: Ganos Peak-800m, 6. V. 1913, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: Tekirdagh province, Ganos Peak-800m, 7. V. 1913, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: GREECE, Évros province: Makri Village, 21. IV. 1914, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: BULGARIA, Rhodopes: Fotinovo Village, 20. VI. 1924, leg. D. Iltchev & P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Gotse Delchev, 5. VI. 1936, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Belassitsa Mountain: 7. VI. 1936, leg. Kr. Touleshkov; 1 ♀: Sturgatch Mountain, 15. VI. 1938, leg. P. Drensky; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: Murtchaevo Village, 18. V. 1939, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain-1650m, 26. VI. 1939, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Isskar Valley: Pantcharevo Village, 26. VII. 1940, leg. Hr. Lukov; 1 ♀: Iskar Valley: Novi Iskar, 10. VIII. 1944, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Vitosha Mountain: Vladaya Village, 8. V. 1949, leg. Iw. Buresch; 1 ♀: Sakar Mountain: 26. V. 1957, leg. N. Atanassov & V. Petrov; 1 ♀: Petritch, 21. VI. 1960, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Strouma Valley: Marino Pole Village, 29. V. 1961, leg. N. Atanassov; 1 ♀: Stara Zagora, 8. VI. 1961, leg. N.

¹ Each specimen in the series has a testaceous colored circle label as a locality code

Atanassov; 1♀: Strouma Valley: Kresnensko Defile Gorge, 7. VI. 1967, leg. A. Popov; 1♀: Lozenska Planina Mountain: NW Pasarel Village-820m, 15. VI. 1995, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

39. *Dasylabris (Dasylabris) mixta* (Er. André, 1903)

Material: 1♀: IRAN, Kerman: Galitchah - Dakido, 19. VI. 1898, leg. N. Zarudnij.

40. *Dasylabris (Inbaltilla) regalis* (Fabricius, 1793)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Rhodopes: Mandritsa Village, 19. VI. 1969, leg. N. Atanassov; 1♀: BULGARIA, Maleshevska Planina Mountain: SW Gorna Breznitsa Village-780m, 21. VIII. 2002, leg. T. Ljubomirov.

41. *Dasylabris deckeni signaticeps* Er. André, 1908

Material: 1♀: ETHIOPIA, Abyssinia, 1935, leg. N. Radeff.

Fig. 4. *Dasylabris bucharensis* (Skorikov) - female - general appearance

*42. *Stenomutilla (Stenomutilla) bizonata* (F. Smith, 1856)

Material: 1♂: BULGARIA, Maritsa Valley: Ognyanovo Village, 3. X. 1960, leg. N. Atanassov.

The male from Ognyanovo Village (Central Bulgaria) has red mesosoma (except for the blackish sternal part) and red tegulae thus corresponding to the colour recently found in Greece (NONVEILLER, 1994)

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**Сбирката от мутилидни оси в Националния
природонаучен музей в София (Нуменоптера: Mutillidae)**

Тoшкo ЛЮБОМИРОВ

(Р е з ю м е)

Установени са 42 вида от 18 рода ципокрили насекоми от семейство Mutillidae в сбирката на Националния природонаучен музей в София. Направена е преценка на използването жилкуването на предното крило при видовете *Krombeinella longicollis* (Tournier), *K. thracia* (Suárez) и *K. beaumonti* (Invega), като е установено, че то няма стойност като белег за разграничаване на тези видове. *Skorikovia radoszkovskii* (Skorikov) е съобщен като нов за фауната на Турция. *Krombeinella nigriceps nigriceps* (S. Saunders), *Dentilla curtiventris* (Er. André), *Physetopoda daghestanica* (Radoszkovsky), *Ph. lucasii lucasii* (F. Smith), *Ph. pusilla*, *Skorikovia pliginskiji* (Skorikov), *Smicromyrme ausonia ausonia* Invega, *Trogaspidia catanensis* (Rossi), *Cystomutilla ruficeps* (F. Smith) и *Stenomutilla bizonata* (F. Smith) са съобщени като нови за фауната на България.